

Interaction of Chloranil with some Primary Aliphatic Amines

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The appearance of a new absorption band, often in the visible region, in amine-tetrahalo-p benzoquinone system is generally believed to be due to the formation of molecular complex. In a number of instances¹⁻³, however, the optical density of these solutions has been found to change with time and in some cases the solutions become turbid on standing due to precipitation¹, even in nitrogen atmosphere.⁵ Earlier works on these systems were mainly concerned with measurements on the new absorption band, believed to be the charge transfer band and apparently no attempt was made either to identify the precipitate or to establish the presence of a reversible equilibrium in the mixture. This, together with the well known fact that two of the halogen atoms of the tetrahaloquinones are very reactive and are easily replaced by hydroxyl, amino and a large number of other groups^{6,7}, prompted us to undertake a systematic investigation of these systems. A brief account of the results of our investigation on the interaction between chloranil and some aliphatic amines are reported here.

EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Chloranil (Fluka, pure) was crystallised several times from benzene. n-Hexyl amine and cyclohexylamine (Reagent grade) were distilled before use, while ethyl amine (78% v/v in water, B.D.H.) was used without further purification. All solvents were E. Merck's proanalyst quality. Spectrophotometric measurements were done with Carl-Zeiss V.S.U.-1 spectrophotometer. Chloranil concentration employed was of the order of 10^{-3} M while that of amine varied between 10^{-4} and 0.1M. Always freshly prepared solutions were used.

As reported by earlier workers on amine chloranil systems, the optical densities were found to change with time and precipitation occurred in many solutions depending on the concentrations of the components. With high amine concentrations (100 or more times that of chloranil) constant values of O. D. were obtained within 1-2 hr. The final spectra of these solutions were similar on all the cases, each exhibiting two strong absorption bands in the U. V. region at 222 m μ and 354 m μ and a broad weak band in the visible region at about 520-530 m μ in methanolic solutions. In carbon tetrachloride solutions peaks were observed at 354 m μ (strong) and 520-530 m μ (weak and broad).

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Liberation of hydrochloric acid from amine chloranil mixture in carbontetrachloride was confirmed by shaking the mixture with water and testing the aqueous layer for chloride ion. Blank tests were also performed.

When the amine chloranil mixture containing excess amines were concentrated and the excess amine was removed by acid washing, followed by washing with dilute alkali, water and finally dehydrated with anhydrous sodium sulphate, coloured solids were obtained, which were recrystallised from methanol—Pet. ether mixture. The melting points and elemental analysis of these solids are given below.

Solid obtained from:	M.P. %	Molecular formula of the disubstituted chloranil	Analysis (%)	
			Found	Reqd.
Chloranil-n-hexyl- amine	180	$C_{18}H_{28}O_2N_2Cl_2$	C, 57.70	57.61
			H, 7.45	7.47
			N, 7.46	7.47
Chloranil-cyclo- hexyl amine	226	$C_{18}H_{24}O_2N_2Cl_2$	C, 58.30	58.22
			H, 6.45	6.47
			N, 7.60	7.55
Chloranil-ethyl amine	243	$C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2Cl_2$	C, 48.54	48.66
			H, 4.52	4.56
			N, 10.58	10.64

The spectra of these solids in solution were found to be identical with those of the corresponding amine chloranil mixture. These facts, therefore, unequivocally suggest that the colour of the amine chloranil mixture is not due to any charge transfer complex formation, but due to the formation of the disubstituted product.

As the O.D of the solutions (amine concentration higher than that of chloranil) changes quite rapidly, reliable spectra of amine chloranil system, *immediately after mixing*, could not be obtained. However, amine chloranil mixture in methanol with amine concentration *much lower* than that of chloranil, the O.D changes so slowly that reliable spectra could be obtained immediately after mixing. The yellow colour of these solutions deepens immediately on mixing. On examination of the spectra, it was found that the change of the colour is not due to any formation of the disubstituted product which has been shown to be responsible for the absorption in the visible region in solutions containing excess amines. The spectra in these cases do not exhibit the expected strong peak at 354 m μ , although the absorbance values were found to increase appreciably in the range 400-450 m μ . A detailed analysis of the O.D. data of n-hexyl amine chloranil system in methanol, which will be communicated later on to this journal, indicates the formation of 1-1 complex between the amine and chloranil.